

AN ANALYSIS OF OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN INDIA

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Cite This Article: Dr. D. Lakshmi, "An Analysis of Opportunities and Challenges in Higher Education in India", International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Modern Education, Volume 8, Issue 2, Page Number 39-43, 2022.

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Abstract:

The Economic success of any country mostly determined on the basis of higher education prevailed in the country. Power of knowledge is the strength of a nation. Hence we can define the developed nation is an educated nation. India has long history in the world of education but it still has not achieved success after 75 years of independence. Indian higher education system is the third largest in the world next to United States and China. India needs more transparency and accountability in the education system since we have seen some fake institutes, fake certificates and plagiarism etc., threatening India and lowering its images in the several indicators of world Index on higher education. Hence in this context the researcher make an attempt to explore the opportunities and challenges in India.

Key Words: NEP, Inclusive Growth, Students Teacher Ratio.

Introduction:

After independence of 75 years, India is still far behind in higher education while compare to the world countries. India's contribution to educational sector is only less than 3% of GDP (Gross Domestic Product) which is very less and its innovation in the educational sector is also a great concern for us. According to the World Bank collection of development indicators the rural population in India was reported at 64.61 % in 2021. However, there is hardly any attention being paid to the education system existing in rural India. Many villages in India do not have the accessibility of transport, communication, drinking water, electricity, internet facility etc. These infrastructure developments are very much essential for bringing inclusive growth in education. The universities, colleges in urban areas are also not providing advance facilities such as uninterrupted internet access, computer labs, science laboratory, advanced text books, journals, digital library, smart class room etc.. And many colleges and universities contribution in research area is very less and are not providing adequate financial support to the students for doing research, invention and innovation in their specialization subject. Hence in this aspect the researcher focuses on the various inadequacies in Indian system of education highlighting the opportunities, challenges and drawbacks of Indian higher Education System.

Objectives of the Study:

- To give an overview of Indian education sector
- To identify the opportunities available in Higher Education
- To analyze the challenges of Educational Institution in India.
- To give suggestions to overcome the present challenges and drawbacks.

Data Collected:

Only Secondary data is used for the analysis. The secondary data is collected through Publication of Government of India, news paper, articles, magazines through internet and form e-resources.

Overview of higher Education System in India:

Indian education has a long early history in the world. In India the education starts in the vedic period itself where India follows the 'Gurukul System' teaching and learning process revolved around in Gurukulum wherein the student students stay for a particular period of time along with the guru. It was a residential concept wherein the students were educated under the guidance of a "Guru". They teach the different areas of religion, philosophy and science. After the British invasion education system in India finds a radical change wherein the learning system was focused in English mode for the British administrative services, army and trade in India. English mode British model of University system continued to expand across India, leading to a rising number of higher learning centers by 1947.

At the time of independence India had 20 universities, 500 colleges enrolling about 2,30,000 students. The higher education system in India grew rapidly after independence with the introduction five year plans. By 1980, there were 132 universities and 4738 colleges in higher education. This number has increased to 659 Universities and 33023 colleges up to December 2011-12. India educates approximately 10 per cent of its youths in higher education.(Knowledge Review Magazine). UGC recently released a report describing the current scenario of the Indian Higher Education System shows that despite the growing numbers of colleges and

enrollments, it is not adequate enough to cater to the educational needs of the increasing young population. The following is some of the highlights and overviews of higher education system in India.

Expenditure on Education in India:

Expenditure on education in India is very less while compare to the China, U.S., Brazil etc. Last seven years expenditure on education spent by India is very less. More than 45% of population lives in rural area and are under privileged.. Even after the introduction of Right to information Act 2005 India still not achieve to provide inclusive education because of lower contribution of education expenditure by the government. In order to provide world class education Government should spare considerable amount in the higher education. NEP 2020 (National Education Policy 2020) aims to spare Education expenditure on GDP 6% to provide world-class quality education, and provide financial support for research, invention, and innovation and improve its position in the world record in all aspects of higher education

The table shows expenditure on education during 2014-15 to 2021-22

Year	Education Expenditure as % of GDP
2021-22	3.1%
2019-20	3.1%
2018-19	2.8%
2017-18	2.8%
2016-17	2.7%
2015-16	2.6%
2014-15	2.4%

Source: Indian Express

The above table reveals that India’s actual expenditure on education is only around 3% . Even after the introduction of NEP 2020 India’s contribution is only less than 3%. It is suggested that India take effective measures to overcome this barrier and contribute more on higher education to bring world class education and attain knowledge power country in the world.

No of Universities in India from 2015 to 2021:

At the time of independence India has only 20 universities and 496 colleges. It is gradually increased with the help of private contribution in establishing the universities and college. At present 1057 universities, 15.03 lakh teachers 385 lakh students in India in Higher education.

Table shows number of universities in India 2015-2022

Year	No. of Universities in India
2022	1057
2020	1043
2019	993
2018	903
2017	864
2016	799
2015	760

Source: ugc.c.in

It reveals that the number universities increases every year but it is not sufficient to meet the needs of increased population.

Classification of universities in India:

Classification of universities	No. of Universities in India (23.08.22)
Central Universities	54
State universities	456
Deemed to be universities	126
Private Universities	421
Total	1057

Source: ugc.ac.in

The above data reveals that private universities playing a huge role in higher section sector. Government contributions are less in the higher educational sector. Hence it is stated that the government should focus to increase its contribution then only the under privileged people enjoy the right to education.

India’s Gross Expenditure on Research:

Sustained Growth in developed nations is attributed by their expenditure on Research & Development. Government expenditure on R&D is less in India while compare to the world countries contribution.

Table shows Gross Research and Development (R&D) expenditure worldwide

Country name	Gross Research and Development In billion U.S Dollars (2022)
United states	679.4

China	551.1
Japan	182.2
Germany	143.1
South Korea	106.1
France	68.5
India	65.2
United kingdom	54.9
Russia	52.2
Brazil	37

Source: Statista.com

The above data reveals that India placed in 7th position among the world top countries Gross Research and Development. Hence it is suggested that the Government should extend its support on Research & Development to fetch the objectives of NEP 2020.

According to NITI Aayog's India Innovation Index 2021 India's gross expenditure on research and development (R&D) is one of the lowest in the world, with just \$43 per capita. This shows that India needs to boost this expenditure and at least be on a par with its BRICS or ASEAN counterparts like Russia (\$285), Brazil (\$173), and Malaysia (\$293). India's gross expenditure on R&D (GERD) as a percentage of GDP has been consistent and hovered around 0.7% for about a decade. This is even lower than Brazil (1.16%), South Africa (0.83%) and others..

Opportunities in Higher Education in India:

Though Covid 19 has many negative impacts on all over the world and brings many changes in political, economical and social arena. It totally affects the health of people and total life pattern has completely changed during covid period. But at the same time one remarkable change has happened in the country is adopting ICT (Information Communication & Technology) tools in educational sector. All teachers, irrespective of age group forced to adopt the on line teaching mode which enhances the knowledge of teacher's in using ICT tools to connect the students through Google meet, Zoom meet Skype etc., Power point presentation with pictorial representation make the students to understand clearly and easily the subjects taught by the teacher. Conducting quiz using Google forms, Getting assignment through Google Class rooms are all used by the teachers to evaluate the students performance. Hence in the present situation it is easy to adopt the technological changes in educational sector by the Institution as well as the teachers and student subject to some drawbacks like of lack of connectivity, power shut down etc. In addition to that many students find difficult to get Android mobile phone.

With the help of the Central and State Government funds, NGO's (Non-Governmental Organization) aids and private people participation, the educational institutions modify or reconstruct or bring the new laboratory to present perspective of NEP 2020 which enhance the teachers and students engagement in research for bringing new idea, new theories or new product development or design whatever it is possible through the advanced laboratory.

As per the NAAC (National Assessment and Accreditation Council) requisition now the institution are ready to sign with the memorandum of understanding with many industries, MSME's, (Ministry of Micro, Small & medium Enterprises) Government organization for the skill development programme, Industrial Visit, Entrepreneurship Development Programmes for all streams of student science, commerce, arts etc., The collaborative agreements within the country or outside the country make the students to do more research in their specified area. NIDHI (National Initiative for Development and Harnessing Innovations), SERB (Science and Engineering Research Board) and Awards like Inspire Awards MANAK (Million Minds Augmenting National Aspirations and Knowledge) etc. induce the students to bring innovative startup and get patent for their innovations.

The interdisciplinary system like twinning degree or /Dual Degree/ Joint degree introduced by some of the institution enable the students to acquire more knowledge in other fields apart from their area of study. With the advent of NEP 2020 India has the scope to collaborate with foreign institution to start up their institution in India and Indian institution can also start their institution outside India make the country to avail the quality education in better way and in wider perspective.

Government of India introduces the new versions of many Digital Learning Platform like SWAYAM (Study Webs of Active-Learning for Young Aspiring Minds) and MOOCS (Massive Open Online Course). The teachers can act as the content provider or content creator to the various digital learning platforms also. The teachers or students take up any course through online mode with free of material in the form of text, video or audio form. When he/she wants to enrich her knowledge in other field they equip themselves to the present digital leaning mode and get the certificates.

Challenges in India:

The age group for higher (tertiary) education is 18-22 years internationally. As per the international standard the higher education GER for India would be 30.6%. While it is higher than Pakistan (9) and

Bangladesh (21), it is comparatively less than other countries in Asia – China (51), South Korea (94), Malaysia (45), Indonesia (36), Iran (70) etc. Globally, USA's higher education GER is 88, UK's is 60, Germany is at 70 and Canada's is 69 etc (Factly October 22 2019). Teachers in India are not well qualified. Since 60% of institution is run by the private, the institution without following the Government norms, appointed the young people as faculty who have no qualification and experience. They appointed the teachers with less amount of salary, since they run the educational institution as business oriented purpose. Even the NET., Ph.D candidates are in unemployed status since the private institution appointing the unqualified staff with less amount of salary.

Nearly 22% of higher educational institutions are in the accreditation process. 26% of Institutions don't apply for the NAAC (National Assessment and Accreditation Council) since they lack permanent faculty and 5.5% are not having permanent head of the institution. According to ministry sources at present there are 600 unaccredited universities and 25,000 unaccredited colleges in India (May 5 2020 Times of India). Lack of funding is another problem for qualitative research work. Only the central and state universities and IITs' (Indian Institute of Technology) and REC's (Regional Engineering Colleges) receiving the funding from the central government for research and innovation. Complicated formalities are great restriction for the institutions to avail subsidy or financial support from the government which act as great impetus for the teachers and students to do the research.

Poor quality of curriculum i.e., the out dated syllabus followed by the universities and colleges. The syllabus is not updated to the present need. Many institutes in India is running without proper infrastructure facilities like library, canteen, transport, computer lab, other science lab, lacking internet facility, sports ground, library etc., In addition to that the institution are lacking with other amenities like, canteen, rest rooms, first aid room, hostels etc., As per the ministry's All India Survey on Higher Education statistics, while the student enrolment in higher education institutes have increased from 32.3 million in 2013-14 to 36.6 million in 2017-18, the total number of teachers have declined from 13,67,535 to 12,84,755

According to estimates, the country's higher education sector -- central, state and private universities -- is facing a shortfall of over 5 lakh teachers. "India is short of professors, with 6,600 posts vacant in central universities, a shortfall of 33 per cent. In IITs and state universities, 35 per cent and 38 per cent vacancies need to be filled respectively," the report stated (India Today July 14 2019). This brings adverse effect in student-teacher ratio. The student – teacher ratio of 24:1 in India is lower than 19:1 in Brazil and China. Among the eight countries compared, India's student-ratio has turned out to be the lowest - against Sweden's 12:1, Britain's 16:1, Russia's 10:1 and Canada's 9:1. (India today July 14 2019).

The problem of student's teacher ratio brings adverse effect in higher deduction system. The overburdened teachers are also unable to pursue any research or encourage their students to do so. As a sequel the quality of education provided to them is decreased tremendously because of the focus of more students instead of the required student's teacher's ratio. Number of research papers published in India is increased but the impact factor journal publishing is very less when compare to China, U.S. Germany etc., and it is great concern for India. India stands in the top position in plagiarism which is a great impetus for us to show our excellence in the global level of education and research.

In higher educational institution there is very limited no. of collaboration only made with the industries within a country and outside the country. Low employability is another problem as many graduates are still unemployed status. Limited number of higher institution is another problem. Many villages, rural area no colleges, even there is no school at all. Ministry of Rural Development stated that around 13,511 villages do not have schools all across states in India. Out of 5,97,618 inhabited villages in the country, 25,067 villages lack mobile connectivity and Internet, according to the Ministry of Communications reply in the Lok Sabha based on Telecom Service Providers (TSP) data

The University Grants Commission (UGC) declared 24 "self-styled" institutions fake and found two more in violation of norms. Delhi has eight such fake universities like All India Institute of Public & Physical Health Sciences, Commercial University Ltd. Daryaganj, United Nations University, Vocational University, etc., Uttar Pradesh has seven such fake universities - Gandhi Hindi Vidyapith, National University of Electro Complex Homeopathy, Netaji Subhash chandra Bose University (open university) etc., Apart from these, universities from Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, West Bengal, Odisha, Puducherry and Andhra Pradesh are also listed (Indian Express 2022). The fake universities are also great concern for India which affects students of higher education morality confidence, hope etc. Institutions only teaching ethics but in reality, the institution itself do the malpractice how they generate good citizens and how they bring good researcher, educator, scientist to India.

Suggestions:

Government expenditure on education is very less after the introduction of NEP 2020 also. Hence it is suggested that more funds must be provided for the science projects, laboratory research and under privilege students' scholarship and other aids for the enrollment of people with poor back ground.

The government should take initiative to start many colleges and universities near the rural areas In addition to that the students those who comes from very low financial background the government must extend

supportable activities like providing textbooks, guiding them the e-resources availability, library and laboratory facilities which make the student attend the class interestingly without dropout.

The government should monitor and appoint teachers immediately without any delay when there is a vacancy arises in the government and government aided institution and keep watching on the students teachers ratio maintained at the agreed level, then only the students focused by the teachers efficiently without overburden of additional work arising on vacancies

The government and institution should take initiatives for conducting workshops, orientation, refresher courses seminars, conferences etc. to improve the knowledge of teachers to adopt the present technology and bring new pedagogy in the curriculum. Out dated syllabus must be removed and the curriculum subjects must be updated according the present expectation in the national, international job market.

Many skill development programs must be conducted by the institution to make the student to become the entrepreneur or to become scientist according to the nature of study they pursue. Every institution should adopt multi disciplinary approach which enhances the students to get more knowledge apart from their area of study The government should extend more financial support to the institutions for doing research projects and publishing research papers in national and international journal, and also provide aid to infrastructure development of labs, library, smart class room etc.. which enhances the students to bring many start ups in various fields to meet the standards of global level..

In order to use ICT tools by the students and teachers, the Government should take initiative to provide uninterrupted power supply and uninterrupted internet facility, proper road facility, communication etc.

Conclusion:

After the globalization and digitalization the world becomes “flat” with goods and services, and people move from one country to another for education and employment. After covid 19 there are many radical changes happened in the higher education system all over the world. It is inevitable to follow the blended learning system with the help of ICT tools, e-resources, artificial intelligence in the class rooms by the teacher. As per the objectives NEP 2020 Indian universities and Institution must adopt these changes by giving orientation, refresher courses, workshop etc. to enable the teachers and student to follow ICT tools enabled learning process. Outcome Based Education (OBCE) is needed in the present situation hence, every institution and teaches adopt these changes in their curriculum in righteous way and effectively, which entails India stands knowledge power country in the world. Government also extends financial support and other infrastructure facilities to the institution to bring world class quality education in the country.

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